

But the breakdown of blast resistance is common in many rice-growing areas, often shortly after the release of culti-

vars with race-specific resistance. We should therefore develop breeding strategies for durable resistance to

reduce the impact of rice blast disease by using the abundant rice genetic resources of Yunnan and Japan. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

Karnataka rice hybrids

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For more than a decade, farmers in the irrigated area of Karnataka harvested yields of up to 7 t ha⁻¹. No new technologies could help them increase yield further. Therefore, the major objective of the hybrid rice research begun at Mandya was to identify a suitable hybrid that could yield at least 1 t more than the check varieties. This objective was fulfilled by the release in 1994 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and in 1996 of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 (KRH2). The hybrid KRH1 (IR58025A/IR9761-19-1R) has a yield potential of 7.5-8.5 t ha⁻¹ and matures in 125 d. In 150 on-farm irrigated trials conducted in farmers' fields in different districts, KRH1 had a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over the check varieties. This hybrid possesses field tolerance for major pests and diseases.

Medium-duration hybrid KRH2 (IR58025A and KMR3) matures in 135 d and yields at least 1.0 t ha⁻¹ more than the best check variety, Jaya. In addition, it has a better straw yield and exhibits tolerance for blast. Therefore, farmers are impressed by its performance. This hybrid is semitall with long, slender grains. In 15 other trials conducted at Mandya from 1992 to 1995, KRH2 produced an average of 9.3 t ha⁻¹ with a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya. Similarly, multilocation, multiseasonal experiments conducted at different research stations in Karnataka in irrigated areas also confirmed the superiority of KRH2, with at least 1.2 t ha⁻¹ more yield than Jaya. This hybrid was found to be more stable over locations. KRH2 recorded the highest yields in national trials during 1995, with a yield

advantage of more than 0.9 t ha⁻¹ over Jaya.

Agronomic experiments with these hybrids indicated that the recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for semidwarf varieties is also suitable for these hybrids. Planting one seedling hill⁻¹ and 20- × 10-cm spacing are recommended for this hybrid. A seed rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ is sufficient. ■

TNRH16: a salt-tolerant rice hybrid

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Among abiotic stresses, salinity-alkalinity is the major constraint to yield in rice. Experience in other crops indicates that hybrids perform better than varieties under adverse growing conditions. A study was therefore made to evaluate hybrids involving salt-tolerant parental lines. Ten male sterile lines with their respective B lines and 24 restorer lines were screened under natural salt-stress conditions (pH 9.0

and EC 0.21 dS m⁻¹). Of these, IR62829A, IR66707A, and IR58025A were more tolerant. A similar response was recorded in their respective B lines. Of the 24 restorer lines, only six had good phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth. Assuming that the additive complementary effect of tolerant A and R lines in the hybrid would enhance the level of salt tolerance, hybrids involving such parental lines were evaluated for salt tolerance. All F₁ hybrids derived using IR62829A and IR58025A as male sterile lines, though poor yielders, proved quite tolerant, with high phenotypic acceptability at all stages of growth from seedling to flowering. A high pollen or spikelet number during the last phase possibly resulted in poor grain yields. TNRH16, derived from moderately salt-tolerant parents (IR58025A/C20R), was the only exception. This hybrid recorded a grain yield of 5,002 kg ha⁻¹, whereas the salt-tolerant check, Co 43, recorded 4,160 kg ha⁻¹. The standard heterosis was 23%. The higher grain yield of TNRH16 may also be attributed to the fact that parental characters for sodicity tolerance get complemented in the F₁ hybrid. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Differentiation of rice tungro spherical virus variants by RT-PCR and RFLP

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Rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) is one of the two causal agents of rice tungro disease, the most important viral disease of rice in South and Southeast Asia. RTSV assists in the semipersistent transmission of rice

tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), the other causal agent, which causes the symptoms.

RTSV is a single-stranded RNA virus of 12,180 nucleotides (Hull 1996). Genome organization shows that it encodes a large polyprotein of 393 kDa, which contains the three coat proteins (CP1, CP2, and CP3), motifs for nucleotide triphosphate (NTP) binding domain, protease (PRO), and polymerase (POL). The polyprotein is thought to be cleaved by the virus-

1. Western blot of coat proteins (CP) 1, 2, and 3 of RTSV strains A and Vt6. CPs were separated by SDS-PAGE, transferred to a nylon membrane, and incubated with polyclonal antiserum and antiserum specific to each CP. The size of the molecular weight markers (in kiloDaltons) is indicated on the left. H = healthy extract.

and/or cell-encoded proteases. The genome also contains two short open reading frames at the 3' end. Recent studies have demonstrated that rice cultivars react differently to RTSV variants. TKM6, resistant to type variant A, is susceptible to the RTSV-Vt6 variant (Cabauatan et al 1995). Discrimination between these two variants cannot be achieved by serological means (Fig. 1).

To look for polymorphic molecular markers that will differentiate the two RTSV variants, specific oligonucleotides were used to amplify the coat protein gene fragments of RTSV by reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). The CP1-2 region was then selected, amplified using RSCP1V2453 and RSCP2C3607 primers, and digested with different restriction enzymes. RSCP1V corresponds to nucleotides (nt) 2453 to 2472 and RSCP2C corresponds to nt 3548 to 3607 in the RTSV-A RNA nucleotide sequence.

Briefly, the first-strand cDNA synthesis was performed using 0.1 ng of purified virus or 1 µg of total RNA extracts and RSCP2C primer. The mixture was denatured at 70 °C for 10 min, chilled on ice for at least 1 min, and after the adjustment to 200 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.4), 500 mM KCl, 25 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM dNTP, and 0.1 M DTT in 20 µl total volume, the reaction was incubated at 42 °C for 5 min. Fifty U of

2. Amplification of coat protein regions of RTSV variants by reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). (A) 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis analysis of RT-PCR amplified cDNA using CP1 primers (lane 2), CP2 primers (lane 3), CP3 primers (lane 4), CP1-2 (lane 5), CP2-3 (lane 6), and CP1-3 (lane 7). (B) Autoradiograph of the same gel when blotted onto a nylon membrane and hybridized with an RTSV CP2-3 specific probe. Lane 1, high marker. U = undigested PCR product, H = *HindIII* digested PCR product, B = *BstYI* digested product.

SuperScript II reverse transcriptase (Gibco BRL) were added and the reaction proceeded at 42 °C for 50 min. The reaction was terminated at 70 °C for 15 min followed by a chill on ice. The first-strand cDNA was amplified using PCR mixtures containing 200 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.4), 500 mM KCl, 25 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM dNTP, a mix of RSCP1V and RSCP2C primers, 5 U of Taq polymerase, and the cDNA to make a total volume of 50 µL, and was overlaid with mineral oil. Reaction mixtures were heated at 95 °C for 1 min, 95 °C for 1 min, 50 °C for 1 min, and 68 °C for 5 min for 30 cycles, and at 72 °C, for 7 min as a final extension.

PCR aliquots were analyzed in 1.5% agarose gels, using 45 mM Tris-borate, pH 8.0, 1 mM EDTA (TBE) as electrophoresis buffer. Five µL of the product were restricted with *HindIII* or *BstYI* (*XhoII*) at 37 °C for 16 h in a final volume of 50 µL in the buffer supplied by New England Biolabs Co. Restriction fragments were also observed on 1.5% agarose gels.

Using the RT-PCR technique, the three coat protein regions of both RTSV variants were amplified (Fig. 2). The identity of the PCR products was confirmed by Southern blot hybridization using the RTSV-specific CP2-3 probe (a gift from Dr. R. Hull, JIC, England). Digestion of the RT-PCR products from the CP1-2 region using *HindIII* and *BstYI* showed a distinct

banding pattern between the two RTSV variants (Fig. 3). For RTSV-A, restriction digestion with *HindIII* produced two fragments of about 600 bp each and with *BstYI* two fragments of about 800 bp and 300 bp.

These patterns were identical to those expected from the published sequence of the RTSV CP1-2 region: two fragments of 579 bp for *HindIII* digestion and two fragments of 807 bp and 284 bp for *BstYI* digestion (Shen et al 1993).

For RTSV-Vt6, restriction digestion with *HindIII* did not produce any size change in the PCR product, but with

3. RFLP differences between the RT-PCR products of RTSV variants when digested with *HindIII* or *BstYI*. Lane 1, low biomarker; 2, undigested RTSV A (U); 3, *HindIII* digested RTSV A (H); 4, *BstYI* digested RTSV A (B); 5, undigested RTSV Vt6 (U); 6, *HindIII* digested RTSV Vt6 (H); 7, *BstYI* digested RTSV Vt6 (B).

*Bst*YI, two fragments of about 700 bp and 300 bp were observed. Sequence analysis of the CP1-2 region from RTSV-Vt6 (unpublished results) confirmed the absence of the *Hind*III site and the presence of three fragments after *Bst*YI digestion: 707 bp, 284 bp, and 108 bp. Variation between the two viral strains was confirmed at nt positions 2556 and 3032 based on the published sequence. The RT-PCR method can therefore be used to study RTSV coat protein variation in natural field populations.

References

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- Shen P, Kaniewska M, Smith C, Beachy RN. 1993. Nucleotide sequence and genomic organization of rice tungro spherical virus. *Virology* 193:621-630. ■

Mechanism of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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RTSV is one of two viruses that cause tungro disease. RTSV is independently transmitted, whereas the other virus, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), is dependent on RTSV for its transmission by the green leafhopper (GLH), *Nephotettix virescens*. The occurrence and spread of tungro disease therefore depend on the presence of RTSV in the field. Resistance to RTSV infection would slow down the spread of the disease.

One of the most important components of a tungro management strategy has been the use of resistant varieties. After a few years of intensive cultivation, however, these varieties succumb to tungro infection. Changes in field response to tungro infection have been

attributed to a shift in GLH virulence to the varieties over time as shown by experiments conducted under natural and artificial conditions (Dahal 1988, Dahal et al 1990, Cabunagan and Ling 1982). Although these studies indicate that the mechanism of resistance to tungro might be vector-dependent, other results showed a different phenomenon. For example, GLH selected on Pankhari 203, TAPL 796, and IR20 for 9-19 generations did not cause a significant increase in RTSV transmission to these varieties (Heinrich and Rapusas 1984, Dahal 1988, Hibino et al 1988). Hence, the mechanism of resistance to tungro may not be vector-dependent only and GLH adaptation may not be the only factor involved in resistance breakdown.

In 1995, a new strain of RTSV, designated as Vt6, was isolated from rice variety TKM6 in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines (Cabauatan et al 1995). TKM6 is highly resistant to the IRRI strain of RTSV (strain A) and is the common parent of IR20, IR26, IR30, and IR40. These varieties have moderate resistance to GLH and have shown consistent resistance to RTSV since they were released in the 1970s (Hibino et al 1988). We used IR26 to study the role of GLH adaptation and strain variation in the mechanism of resistance to RTSV and found that resistance to RTSV is both vector- and virus-dependent. GLHs were collected from a field in Polangui, Albay, Philippines, and reared on rice variety TN1 for two generations. The progenies were then

tested for their transmission of RTSV strains A and Vt6 to TN1 (RTSV-susceptible) and IR26 (RTSV-resistant). Afterwards, the GLH colony was divided into two; one-half was reared on TN1 (GLH-susceptible) and the other half on IR26 (GLH-resistant) for 11 generations. The GLH colonies were then tested again for RTSV strain transmission on both TN1 and IR26. Transmission of RTSV strains A and Vt6 by each GLH colony was compared on both varieties before and after selection. RTSV transmission efficiency of selected colonies was also tested on rice varieties TKM6 and Adday Sel., varieties with known resistance to RTSV. All transmission tests were conducted in test tubes at 1 insect seedling⁻¹ for an overnight inoculation access. RTSV was detected in inoculated plants by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

After 11 generations, the GLH colony on IR26 reproduced as well as the one on TN1. It was reported that a biotype of GLH could be selected by being reared on a resistant rice variety (Kobayashi et al 1983); therefore, the GLH colony on IR26 can be considered to be adapted to its host. Transmission tests showed that the reaction of IR26 to RTSV-Vt6 changed from resistant (23% infection rate before selection) to susceptible (62.8% infection rate after 11 generations on IR26), while the reaction of IR26 to RTSV-A remained resistant (0% infection rate) (Table 1).

These results indicate that the resistance of IR26 to RTSV is both

Table 1. Transmission (%) of RTSV strains A and Vt6 to IR26 and TN1 by field-collected GLH before selection on IR26, TN1, TKM6, and Adday Sel. and after selection for 11 generations.

Variety	Before selection ^b		After selection on			
	AC	Vt6 ^c	TN1		IR26	
			A	Vt6	A	Vt6
TN1	97	78	82	82	59	82
IR26	0	23	0	29	0	63
TKM6	-	- ^d	0	59	0	31
Adday Sel.	-	-	0	0	0	0

^aOne insect seedling⁻¹, overnight inoculation access; 40 seedlings treatment⁻¹. ^bField-collected (Bicol) GLH was reared on TN1 for two generations and adult progenies were tested for transmission of RTSV A and Vt6 before selection on IR26. ^cTested by ELISA 3 wk after inoculation. ^dNot tested.